

Flaws in the inclusion of trials and in referring to earlier meta-analyses by Khan (2020)

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Khan et al. have not responded to the PubPeer comment by 2026.

Comment on:

Sher Ali Khan, Sandipan Bhattacharjee, Muhammad Owais Abdul Ghani, Rachel Walden, Qin M Chen.

Vitamin C for Cardiac Protection during Percutaneous Coronary Intervention: A Systematic Review of Randomized Controlled Trials.

Nutrients. 2020 Jul 23;12(8):2199.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12082199>

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7468730>

Khan et al state in their title "*Vitamin C for cardiac protection ...*" and in their abstract "*We address whether intravenous infusion of vitamin C (VC) prior to PCI provides a benefit for cardioprotection*" (1).

However, their Table 1 reveals that **4 out of 8 included trials were not "vitamin C" trials** (1), instead participants in those 4 trials were administered vitamin E or beta-carotene or vitamin A in addition to vitamin C. Thus, the difference between the control group and the intervention group can be due to vitamin E or beta-carotene or vitamin A instead of vitamin C. There is no justification to interpret that the benefits in such trials is caused specifically by vitamin C, although the title and the abstracts makes the reader think so (1).

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

In the Discussion section, Khan writes: “*Three (sic!) systematic reviews with meta-analysis have summarized the benefit of VC for CABG and cardiac surgery patients [45,46,47,48].*”

However, reference [45](ref 2 below) had severe errors. For example, “*In their Fig. 4, Hu et al. stated that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in their Table 1 and text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed*” (3). Therefore the calculations of Hu et al. are not valid.

Khan would have found reference (3) by checking the PubMed page of the Hu paper (4), as the “Comment in” section refers to (3).

In addition, reference [48](ref 5 below) had severe errors. For example, “*The three RCTs missing from Baker and Coleman’s meta-analysis—the first, second, and fourth entries in my table—contribute 680 participants and 203 cases of POAF, and their combined weight in my meta-analysis is 74.6%. Thus, the majority of RCT data from the U.S. trials are missing from the meta-analysis of Baker and Coleman*” (6). Therefore the calculations of Baker are not valid.

Khan would have found reference (6) by checking the PubMed page of the Baker and Coleman paper (7), as the “Comment in” section refers to (6).

Reference [46](ref 8 below) used the random-effects meta-analysis and pooled studies that were inconsistent (9). It is much more informative to search for potential explanations for the observed heterogeneity rather than pool incompatible trials together (9). Another meta-analysis searched and found explanations for the heterogeneity in the effects of vitamin C on post-operative atrial fibrillation (10), but this was not cited by Khan (1).

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